

Designing an E-Booklet Script to Promote Semendo Coffee from South Sumatera

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to develop a booklet to promote Semendo Coffee from South Sumatera. This research methodology was Research and Development (R&D) modified by Plom, T. (1997). The stages were 1) Preliminary investigation, 2) Design, 3) Realization/Construction, 4) Test, Evaluation, and 5) Revision, and Implementation. To achieve the purpose, the stages of research and Development were linked to the structure by Sitepu (2004) namely the cover, front part, text part, and back part. Then an ebooklet was made from the promotional media. This e-booklet was tested by an expert. The script was written in English and the design used Canva as the software. The script described the history of Semendo Coffee at PT. Cap Sendok Mas, Process of Semendo Coffee, and Marketing at PT. Cap Sendok Mas.

Keywords: *design, e-booklet, Semendo Coffee from South Sumatera*

INTRODUCTION

At this time coffee has become a lifestyle for all circles of society. Coffee enthusiasts do not only come from among adults, but also many come from among teenagers. Now drinking coffee has become a social necessity to accompany them to work or just chatting.

Semendo Coffee is a local coffee originating from Muara Enim, South Sumatra. Unfortunately, Semendo did not host in South Sumatra. It is not among the highest coffee production in South Sumatra. According to the data, the first position that occupies the most production in South Sumatra is Lampung Coffee, followed by North Sumatra Coffee, Aceh Coffee and Bengkulu Coffee (Dataindonesia.id, n.d.). Even the coffee that has received international recognition at the Algiculture Products Competition Valorization Agency is not Semendo Coffee but Pagaralam Coffee (Antara News.com 2021.). Even though Semendo Coffee is also more delicious because Semendo Coffee has a more concentrated taste and thicker texture.

Due to the lack of promotion carried out by the government in the Muara Enim Region,

this Semendo Coffee is less well known and forgotten by the surrounding community and people outside of South Sumatra. Many people do not know about South Sumatra Coffee because it is rare to find South Sumatra Coffee festivals and the lack of people selling regional specialty coffee. Promotion carried out through coffee festivals from each region are also less attractive. Previously the tourism office had carried out a promotion by holding a coffee festival, but it turned out that the promotional media was not effective because it was only carried out at the provincial level, not at the national or international level. And the city tourism office has not carried out promotional media either through print or electronic media. In electronic media, they only discuss coffee that is known to the public. Meanwhile, South Sumatra also have delicious coffee, commonly known as Semendo Coffee.

Therefore, the writer want to discuss Semendo Coffee to promote Semendo Coffee from South Sumatera. Promotion can be done through technology media by designing an e-booklet script about processing Semendo Coffee so that Semendo Coffee is better known by many people. The writer chose the e-booklet because in the current era of globalization, the surrounding community uses social media more as a place to get information. Although there are several ways to promote coffee through coffee festivals, this is not enough to convince the public, so in this final report the writer will design an e-booklet to promote and preserve regional wealth in South Sumatra, namely the city of Palembang.

Based on the description above, the writer is interested in writing a study entitled "Designing an E-Booklet Script to Promote Semendo Coffee from South Sumatera" to provide information and promote South Sumatra Coffee so that it is better known to the world.

METHOD

The writer used research and development methods of Plomp (1997). The Plomp Model is seen as more flexible compared to other models. Therefore, the researcher chose to use plomp

model research design. According Gustaning, (2014) Plomp model consist of five stages, namely 1) preliminary investigation, 2) design, 3) realization/construction, 4) test, evaluation, and revision, 5) implementation. The stages in the plomp model,will be described as follow:

Figure 1. Steps of Research and Development by Plomp

Gustaning, G. (2014) states that the preliminary investigation step is carried out by analyzing the problem or analyzing the needs such as gathering data and analyzing information, defining the problem, and following up of the project. Therefore, in the preliminary study, the writer began the research by carrying out several steps to collect data, namely literature study, observation, and interviews.

Next, designing step aims to design problem solving in designing the model based on the results of working plans or written plans which will be realized in the realization step. In this stage, after the writer collected the data and the information in preliminary investigation, the writer wrote a script (first draft) and insert the script into an e-booklet. In designing the e-booklet, the writer used guidelines, namely the structure of the e-booklet by Sitepu (2012) and the elements of the e-booklet by Zi, and Gunarto (2021). For the application used, the writer used the Canva application to design scripts into an e-booklets.

This step is conducted through producing activities, like developing, creating, and producing models for training or workshop. At this stage, the writer produced the basic form

of the product as the first draft that has been designed. The first draft that have been designed began to be developed and realized

Testing, evaluation and revision are carried out through the process of collecting, processing and analyzing collected information systematically. It is done in order to obtain the results of problem solving. The developed model is tested to have the data for the evaluation, then the data are treated as feedback for model revision.

Implementation is the last stage after evaluation and revision. In this step, the writer has obtained a valid product. In this situation, the script has been approved and there is no possibility of further revision, the final script can be used as narration in Semendo's copy from South Sumatra. The writer can immediately publish the e-booklet through print this e-booklet into a CD for hard copy and in the form of a link for soft copy.

FINDINGS

Literature Study

In the literature study, the writer read and found information from the Sitepu (2004) about the structure that used to make an e-booklet. The writer found the structure include of 1) Cover, that consist of title. 2) Front part, wich is consist of blankpage, title page, preface and table of content. 3) Text part, consist of explanation that will be deliver. and 4) Back part, consist of contact person of the booklet. Meanwhile for the element the writer found from Zi, Winotakiah, and Gunarto, L. (2021) that the elements consist of 1) Consistency, meaning the writer used the consistant color. In here the writer used brown color and grey from the first page until the last page so that the readers feel comfortable while reading it and make the booklet look neater. 2) Format, meaning that the writer used one column because the paragraphs used are long. 3) Organization, meaning that the writer use a structure such as cover, front part, text part and back part. 4) Attractiveness, meaning the writer use the animation such

as moving image and text so that the content more interesting. 5) Font size, meaning that writer used same font.

Observation

The writer used the type of participant observation. Because the limitation of time and cost, the writer only observed Semendo Coffee in Palembang. The writer found the company that produce Semendo coffee, namely PT. Cap Sendok Mas. The writer observed and participated in the process of Semendo Coffee at PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas. The writer found that there are several Semendo Coffee processes, starting from roasting, cooling, grinding, packaging of Semendo coffee at PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas.

Interview

The writer had conducted an interview with Mrs. Bakar as the owner of the Semendo Coffee business in Palembang and the employee at PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas. In the interview the writer used a structured interview where the writer had prepared list of questions before ask. The writer found the information from Mr. Abu bakar regarding the history of Semendo Coffe at PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas. The writer found that PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas is one of Semendo's Coffee businesses in Palembang that has been around since 1982. The beginning of this business was the business of parents who started their business in a small shop under the Ampera Bridge, 7 Ulu, Palembang. Now, PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas has moved to Jl KH Azhari, 14 Ulu, Palembang, near Kampung Al Munawwar. The writer had also found the information from the employess about marketing. The writer found that the marketing did not only sell this coffee in the Ulu area and Palembang city, but also to outside areas, such as Bandung, Surabaya, and Jakarta.

Designing

Figure 2. e-booklet

Cover includes the title. The writer gave a title that describes the contents of the booklet. The writer chose “Semendo” for the cover because the writer wanted to directly tell the point of the booklet. The writer also gave attractive illustration such as the movement of picture and text which also gives an idea to the contents of the booklet. Figure 4.5 displayed the front cover of the booklet.

The front part consists of the title page, preface, and table of contents. On the title page, the writer provided a little addition, namely “from South Sumatra” to emphasized that Semendo coffee comes from South Sumatra. Figure 4.6 displayed the title page.

On the preface page, the writer explained the purpose of the book and gave thanks to the people who helped the writer finish the book. Figure 4.7 displayed the preface.

On the table of contents page, the writer provided pages so that readers can easily find content in the book. Figure 4.8 displayed a table of content.

Text part consist of 1) the history of Semendo Coffe at PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas, 2) process of Semendo Coffe at PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas, and 3) marketing at PT. Kopi Cap Sendok Mas.

Finally, in the back part, the writer provided the contacts person of the e-booklet or the writer of this booklet. Figure 4.13 displayed the back part.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The e-booklet had been revised based on the suggestion from two experts. Based on the expert's suggestions, the changes were made in two aspects, they are English linguistic for the script, and design for the booklet design.

According to the linguistic expert, Mr. Ismet, the first expert of English linguistic commented that the script of the writers was good, it effectively conveys its message in a clear and concise manner. From the expert's comment, it was in accordance with the theory that was

stated by Prastowo (2014) that the information should be explained clearly, concisely, and interesting to be tailored to the age and experience of the reader. But there are still many error, in the text that needed to be revised. Mr. Ismet said that he found errors in punctuation and capitalization. He also said that he found many words that were still abbreviated in the front part and text part of Semendo Coffe script. But for the composition of the script of Semendo Coffe itself, it is good and includes complete information about Semendo Coffe at PT. Cap Sendok Mas Coffee. While Ms. Pratiwi, the second expert of English linguistic also found many grammatical errors in the text of the Semendo Coffee script. These errors have been corrected and revised by the writer, Mr Ismet and Ms Pratiwi that shown in table 4.2

Meanwhile According to Mr. Ori, as a first design expert comment that the design that the writer has made is interesting and accordance with the opinion of Zakiah, L. G., & Winoto, Y. (2021) state that there are elements that make up the booklet design principles, namely as follows: 1) Consistency, meaning that the selection of fonts and colors must be consistent. The writer's design has used the same type of text for titles, subtitles, and content from the first page to the last page where the author chooses the Lovello font type for the title, The Season for the subtitle and Poppins for the content. The author has also chosen consistent colors, namely brown and gray that match the content. 2) Format, meaning that the booklet display uses one column because the paragraphs used are long. The contents of the material are labeled to make it easier for the reader to read and understand. The writer has set the paragraph format on each page in the booklet. 3) Organization, meaning that it is arranged systematically so that it makes it easier for the reader to read and understand the messages contained in the booklet. The writer has used a booklet structure, namely by Sitepu (2004) which consists of cover, front part, text part, and back part. 4) Attractiveness, namely using an interesting combination of animation and symbols to motivate readers to continue reading. The writer has added animation from the canva application. The writer used Canva because the Canva application is easier and there are

many free features that the writer can use. 5) Font size, meaning that the use of letters must fit and not overlap so that readers can read clearly. Here the writer used size 30 for the title, 24 for the subtitle, and 14 for the content 6) Space, meaning that space can be in the form of space around the title, beginning of the paragraph, margins, and other things that need attention to improve the appearance and readability of the message.

Mr. Ori said that the writer has used the same font and font size for the title and subtitle of the first page to the end. The writer chose the Lovello font type for the title, The Season for the subtitle and Poppins for the content. The writer had also chosen consistent colors, namely brown and gray that match the content. But he gave a comment to the writer regarding Margin. He said the writer doesn't need to give the same margins on every page. The writer only needs to adjust the margins with the content on each page. While Mr. Andre as the second design expert said the design that the writer has made is very interesting because it does not only contain text but is accompanied by several images and other elements. He just gave the additional suggestion that it would be great if the writer gave sound to the design. This is because e-booklets are electronic media, which means writers can add elements such as animation or moving pictures and tests so that the readers do not get bored.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In writing this report, the writer used the Research and Development Method by Plomp (1997). The steps are Preliminary Study, realization/construction, testing, evaluation, and revision, and implementation. In the Preliminary Study step, had collected the data and information through documentation, observation and interviews. In the design step, the writer had designed an e-booklet used the guideline namely structure by Sitepu (2004) and elements by Gunarto (2020). In the realization/construction step, the writer had produced the results as a first draft that the writer has made. Then, in the testing, evaluation, and revision steps, the

writer had tested the first draft to experts for comments and suggestions. Finally, after an e-booklet has been approved and there will be no further revisions it can be used as the E- booklet of Semendo Coffee from South Sumatra as a medium for promoting South Sumatran coffee. The writer had printed this e-booklet into a CD for hard copy and in the form of a link for soft copy.

Based on the design results of the e-booklet script to promote Semendo Coffee from South Sumatra, the writer gives some suggestions for the Muara Enim government to further promote Semendo Coffee. The writer also gives suggestions regarding promotional media that can be used preferably using technological media, namely E- booklets because nowadays many people are more interested in reading information using their cell phone.

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